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Formation of children as personalities at school through music lessons

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Annotation: This article presents the formation of personality with the help of music

Key words: music, school, child, musical space, the meaning of music teaching.

The quality of a modern music lesson is largely determined by the activity of children, the use of methods that arouse their interest, from the individual approach of the teacher to each student. But the presence of a music cabinet and its equipment is of great importance. In recent years, great changes have taken place in the field of education: computer classes, modern technologies appear, the Internet penetrates into the life of the school. An aesthetic design is necessary for the music room, which should contribute to creating the atmosphere necessary for an art lesson, a creative lesson; it is necessary to have children's musical instruments and preferably two sets; visual aids, interactive whiteboards, projectors are currently appearing in schools, with which you can show a better image on the full screen; records have gone into the deep past, a computer with CDs has appeared, which also ensures purity and sound quality. All this makes the lesson interesting, one can say exciting, having a greater impact on the emotions and feelings of schoolchildren, but nothing in the lesson will replace "live" music - the teacher's performance of works on a musical instrument, his exciting word, instilling in the souls of children a love for the beautiful, teaching them to correctly perceive the musical image, his mood.

Music, directly affecting the feelings and consciousness of the student, forms his moral image. Works of various emotional and figurative content encourage children to empathize. The perception of musical works about native nature fosters a sense of love for the Motherland, Russian folk and classical music evokes a sense of pride, respect and love for their people and their artistic heritage. The genre richness of music helps to perceive heroic images, lyrical mood, humor, fervent dance melodies. Music lessons introduce children to music and the characteristic movements of national dances, which helps schoolchildren to comprehend the individuality of the musical language of each nationality and teaches them to show respect for the world heritage.

Solving the problems of musical education of schoolchildren requires the teacher to make an optimal choice of methods, depending on the characteristics of musical activity and the capabilities of students. Success accompanies a teacher who takes a creative approach to the matter, including not only the active part of the class, but also low-initiative students. By arousing children's interest in music, the teacher enriches their inner world, generating a sense of joy and satisfaction in their souls.

The collective actions of the class contribute to the solution of educational tasks - these are singing, games, musical and rhythmic movements, playing children's musical instruments - moments when children are united by common actions that require common efforts from all participants, and common experiences create a beneficial ground for common development. Various types of activities, their alternation, tasks require children's attention, good reaction, organization - this is the simultaneous beginning and ending in the performance of a song, dance, accompaniment on children's instruments, the ability to obey music, restraining natural children's instincts to hurry, overtake - all this educates the child's will, a sense of responsibility, camaraderie, forms moral qualities the identity of the student.

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All types of activities in the music lesson are closely related to mental processes, that is, they require attentiveness, observation, intelligence. Creative tasks are of great importance, that is, problem-searching situations that require high mental activity: children improvise, create their own versions of melody, accompaniment, rhythmic pattern for a certain text, dance movements, depict some character of a game or fairy tale, using expressive movements, facial expressions, gestures, while children stop shy, become more relaxed.

The meaning of teaching music at school is that, while studying music, children are in the process of active creative activity. They sing and play themselves, learning not only to perceive the beauty of musical works, but also to work hard, creating it "with their own hands". The active nature of music lessons teaches you to see the surrounding life better and understand your own spiritual world. Singing in a choir and playing in an orchestra of children's musical instruments develop in children a sense of responsibility for the collective in which they participate. Asafyev B.V. He wrote: "A person who has experienced the joy of creativity, even to the smallest extent, deepens his life experience, becomes different in his psychological makeup than a person who only imitated the acts of others."

It should also be remembered that music lessons contribute to improving children's health: singing develops the vocal apparatus, strengthens the vocal cords, promotes the development of coordination of hearing and voice, develops proper breathing (short inhalation and long exhalation); musical and rhythmic movements improve children's posture, develop coordination of movements, quick reaction to changes in tempo or dynamics in music.

Teachers in many countries are still arguing about whether to teach music to all children or only the most gifted. Russian pedagogy answers this question as follows: music, as a profession, should be taught to children who have excellent musical abilities and a special attraction to music. The general musical education should extend to absolutely all children. Thanks to the correct formulation of children's musical education, it is possible to create a solid foundation of musical culture and instill a love of music.

Conclusion: Properly understood and well-organized musical education provides a high level of culture and education for each person, promotes the comprehensive development of the personality, its aesthetic, mental, moral and physical improvement, helping in the formation of a richly and harmoniously developed personality.

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